

OPEN ACCESS

Key Words

Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency,
hematological parameter,
Vegetarian diet

Corresponding Author

Nisha Kaithwas
Department of Psychiatry, N.S.C
Government Medical College,
Khandwa, Madhya Pradesh, India

Received: 12 January 2023

Accepted: 22 February 2023

Published: 25 February 2023

Citation: Harshul Patidar, Sachin Parmar, Rashmi Yadav, Nisha Kaithwas, Priyesh Marskole and Ranjeet Badole, 2023. Estimate Prevalence of Vitamin B₁₂ Deficiency and its Correlation with Hematological Parameters: A One Year Study. Res. J. Med. Sci., 17: 7-10, doi: 10.59218/makrjms.2023.7.10

Copy Right: MAK HILL Publications

Estimate Prevalence of Vitamin B₁₂ Deficiency and Its Correlation with Hematological Parameters: A One Year Study

¹Harshul Patidar, ²Sachin Parmar, ²Rashmi Yadav, ³Nisha Kaithwas, ²Priyesh Marskole and ⁴Ranjeet Badole

¹Department of Pathology, N.S.C. Government Medical College, Khandwa, Madhya Pradesh, India

²Department of Community Medicine N.S.C. Government Medical College Khandwa, Madhya Pradesh, India

³Department of Psychiatry, N.S.C Government Medical College, Khandwa, Madhya Pradesh, India

⁴Department of General Medicine NSC Government Medical College Khandwa, Madhya Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT

Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency is relatively common in Indian population especially in peoples with strictly vegetarian diet. Aim: To estimate prevalence of Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency in different age groups and gender and its correlation with hematological parameters. This study was carried out in 197 individuals. Vitamin B₁₂ levels were measured using a Mindray CL-900i Chemiluminescence Immunoassay Analyzer and CBC was done using Mindray 5 part fully automated hematology analyzer. Results were distributed according to age groups and gender. In the study 197 individuals were included. Amongst which there were 48.7% males and 51.3% females. In total 197 individuals, 78.2% had variable Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency and 21.9% was having sufficient Vitamin B₁₂ levels. 31.5% individuals had Borderline Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency, 28.4% had Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency, 18.3% had severe Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency. Vegetarian individuals usually get affected from deficiency of Vitamin B₁₂. Since there may be severe complications of Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency, so Vitamin B₁₂ supplements and fortification of foods is recommended.

INTRODUCTION

Vitamin B₁₂ is a water-soluble vitamin, it has role in the formation of RBCs and it is also important in the normal functioning of the nervous system^[1]. Vitamin B₁₂ and folic acid combinedly needed for DNA synthesis, synthesis of neurotransmitters and phospholipids by converting homocysteine to methionine^[2,3]. Chief dietary sources are of animal origin of Gille and Schmid^[4] and other sources are fermented foods. Malabsorption and disorders of intestine lead to Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency Just and Kozakiewicz^[5] Strict vegetarian individuals have high risk^[6]. Megaloblastic anaemia is the most common manifestation of B₁₂ deficiency. Ahmed *et al.*^[7] Many individuals have Pancytopenia with raised Mean Corpuscular Volume in CBC. Vitamin B₁₂ is an essential micronutrient that is indispensable for the biological synthesis of macronutrients, red blood cells and DNA, as documented in the literature^[8]. The acquisition of this particular nutrient is reliant upon dietary sources, including animal-derived foods, seaweed and fermented vegetables, as the human body lacks the ability to synthesise it^[9,10]. The extent to which B₁₂ is absorbed and utilised by the body is contingent upon the quantity and form of its consumption through dietary sources^[8]. Given that animal-derived products are the primary source of B₁₂, individuals who adhere to vegan or vegetarian diets are susceptible to inadequate B₁₂ intake and consequent dietary insufficiency^[9]. Inadequacy can also ensue from hindered absorption of vitamin B₁₂ caused by insufficient hydrochloric acid and/or intrinsic factors^[10]. The insufficiency of vitamin B₁₂ is linked to various health complications, which include but are not limited to mild fatigue and anaemia, severe neurological dysfunction, osteoporosis and metabolic diseases. Additionally, there is an elevation in the biochemical markers of disease risk associated with vitamin B₁₂ deficiency. These findings have been documented in various studies^[10-15]. In accordance with epidemiological research, it has been found that there is a correlation between vitamin B₁₂ deficiency and various health conditions such as obesity, gastrointestinal disease, bariatric surgery and renal insufficiency^[16-18]. Research has indicated a correlation between inadequate levels of vitamin B₁₂ and specific ethnic groups^[19], reduced income Allen *et al.*^[20] and certain lifestyle behaviours such as increased alcohol consumption^[15], tobacco or caffeine use Ulvik *et al.*^[21] and a sedentary way of life^[9]. The consistent utilisation of specific pharmaceuticals, for instance, metformin Aroda *et al.*^[22] and proton pump inhibitors^[23], may potentially result in a deficiency of vitamin B₁₂. The prevalence of vitamin B₁₂ deficiency in young adults has not been extensively studied, as it is commonly perceived as a concern primarily affecting the elderly population^[24].

The prevalence rates of vitamin B₁₂ deficiency range from 2.5-60%, differing by age group, gender and ethnicity^[15,25,26]. The majority of research has utilised a threshold of <148 pmol L⁻¹ to establish the presence of vitamin B₁₂ deficiency^[15,26,27]. However, certain studies have suggested a higher threshold (220 pmol L⁻¹) based on the assessment of homocysteine and methyl malonic acid levels, which serve as tissue markers for vitamin B₁₂ deficiency^[15,19,28]. The latest National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey conducted in the United States reports that the prevalence of vitamin B₁₂ deficiency in the general population aged 19 years and older varies from 3-26%, depending on the threshold employed. Moreover, the survey reveals that women exhibit a higher likelihood of being deficient in vitamin B₁₂ than men^[26].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was done in Central India during the period from April 2022 to March 2023. Purposive sampling was done for the selection of the subjects. So, 197 subjects were included in the study after taking their informed consent and was found to be within ethical standards as the Helsinki Declaration was followed. We measured the Vitamin B₁₂ levels using a Mindray CL-900i Chemiluminescence Immunoassay Analyzer and CBC was done using Mindray 5 part fully automated hematology analyzer. Venous blood samples were collected in clot activator serum tube for Vitamin B₁₂ and in EDTA anticoagulant vial for CBC. Samples were tested within 1 hr of collection to minimize variations due to sample aging. Vitamin B₁₂ and CBC estimation was done and results were noted. Results were distributed according to age groups and gender. Data will be entered into excel spreadsheets and analyzed. Quantitative data was expressed in mean and SD while qualitative in proportion or percentages.

RESULTS

In the study 197 individuals were included. Amongst which there were 48.7% males and 51.3% females.

In total 197 individuals, 78.2% had variable Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency and 21.9% was having sufficient Vitamin B₁₂ levels (Table 1).

About 31.5% individuals had Borderline Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency, 28.4% had Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency, 18.3% had severe Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency.

As represented in Table 2, Mean Corpuscular Volume is raised in Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency individuals and there is significant negative correlation between MCV and Vitamin B₁₂ levels. The WBCs count and platelet count also lowered as the severity of deficiency increases.

Table 1: Vitamin B₁₂ levels variation with Age groups (n = no. of subjects) (Total = 197)

Age groups	Normal (211-911 pg mL ⁻¹)				Borderline deficiency (170-211 pg mL ⁻¹)				Vitamin B ₁₂ deficiency (170-100 pg mL ⁻¹)				Severe vitamin B ₁₂ deficiency (<100 pg mL ⁻¹)			
	Male		Female		Male		Female		Male		Female		Male		Female	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Child (0-16 years)	4	2.1	6	3	4	2.1	4	2.1	2	1	3	1.5	3	1.5	2	1
Young adults (17-30 years)	5	2.5	6	3	9	4.6	10	5.1	8	4	7	3.6	5	2.5	4	2.1
Middle-aged adults (31-45 years)	5	2.5	4	2.1	9	4.6	9	4.6	9	4.6	9	4.6	5	2.5	6	3
Old-aged adults (Above 45 years)	7	3.6	6	3	8	4	9	4.6	8	4	10	5.1	5	2.5	6	3

Table 2: Comparison of severity of Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency with Hematological parameters

	Hemoglobin (g dL ⁻¹)	MCV (fl)	MCH (pg)	MCHC (g dL ⁻¹)	WBCs (10 ⁹ L ⁻¹)	Platelets (lakh cumm ⁻³)
Borderline deficiency	9±1	108±9	34±4	31±3	6±1	1.3±0.1
Vitamin B ₁₂ def.	7±1	108±12	32±7	30±4	5±1	0.8±0.2
Severe vitamin B ₁₂ deficiency	5±1	111±9	34±5	32±3	3±1	0.5±0.4

DISCUSSIONS

The clinical manifestation of vitamin B₁₂ deficiency is observed as megaloblastic anaemia, while prolonged deficiency can result in neurological disorders. In addition to its other effects, folate deficiency is also associated with the development of megaloblastic anaemia^[29].

The study findings indicate that a significant proportion of the participants (78.2%) exhibited a deficiency in vitamin B₁₂. This observation is consistent with the findings of Ahmed et al, who reported a vitamin B₁₂ deficiency prevalence of 72.6% in their study population. Ahmed *et al.*^[30] and Sarode *et al.*^[31] In their respective studies of Sen *et al.*^[32] and Hashim and Tahir^[33] have reported a high prevalence rate of 76% for B₁₂ deficiency. Individuals with anaemia who are deficient in vitamin B₁₂ exhibit a mean corpuscular volume (MCV) greater than 100 femtoliters. Our research aligns with the findings of Wheeler *et al.*^[34], which also reported this phenomenon.

CONCLUSION

Vegetarian individuals usually get affected from deficiency of Vitamin B₁₂. Timely estimation of Vitamin B₁₂ levels may helps in early evaluation of deficiency. Since there may be severe complications of Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency, so Vitamin B₁₂ supplements and fortification of foods is recommended.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors are grateful to the technical staff for their cooperation and help rendered.

REFERENCES

- Gibney, M.J., S.A. Lanham-New, A. Cassidy and H.H. Vorster, 2009. Introduction to Human Nutrition. 2nd Edn., Wiley & Sons, ISBN-17: 978-1-4051-6807-6, Pages: 386.
- González, H.F. and S. Visentin, 2016. Micronutrients and neurodevelopment: An update. Arch. Argent. Pediatr., 114: 570-575.
- Sukumar, N., S.B. Rafnsson, N.B. Kandala, R. Bhopal, C.S. Yajnik and P. Saravanan, 2016. Prevalence of vitamin B-12 insufficiency during pregnancy and its effect on offspring birth weight: A systematic review and meta-analysis. Am. J. Clin. Nutr., 103: 1232-1251.
- Gille, D. and A. Schmid, 2015. Vitamin B₁₂ in meat and dairy products. Nutr. Rev., 73: 106-115.
- Just, M.J. and M. Kozakiewicz, 2015. Depressive disorders co-existing with Addison–Biermer anemia—case report. Neuropsychiatr. Dis. Treat., 2015: 1145-1148.
- Pawlak, R., S.J. Parrott, S. Raj, D. Cullum-Dugan and D. Lucus, 2013. How prevalent is vitamin B₁₂ Deficiency among vegetarians? Nutr. Rev., 71: 110-117.
- Ahmed, T., A.S. Rahman, S. Ahmed, A. Siddiqui, A. Javed, J. Kamal and L. Ahmed, 2012. Frequency of vitamin B₁₂ and red cell folate deficiency in macrocytic anaemia. J. Basic Applied Sci., 8: 706-713.
- Green, R., L.H. Allen, A.L. Bjørke-Monsen, A. Brito and J.L. Guéant *et al.*, 2017. Correction: Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency. Nat. Rev. Dis. Primers, Vol. 3. 10.1038/nrdp.2017.54.
- Herrmann, W., H. Schorr, R. Obeid and J. Geisel, 2003. Vitamin B-12 status, particularly holotranscobalamin ii and methylmalonic acid concentrations and hyperhomocysteinemia in vegetarians. The Am. J. Clin. Nutr., 78B1231-136.
- Institute of Medicine, 1998. Dietary Reference Intakes for Thiamin, Riboflavin, Niacin, Vitamin B6, Folate, Vitamin B₁₂, Pantothenic Acid, Biotin and Choline. National Academies Press, Washington, ISBN-17: 978-0-309-06411-8.
- Pinna, K. and E. Whitney, 2011. Normal and Clinical Nutrition. International Edition Edn., Cengage Learning, USA, ISBN-13: 9780840068453.

12. Orris, M.S., P.F. Jacques and J. Selhub, 2005. Relation between homocysteine and B-vitamin status indicators and bone mineral density in older Americans. *Bone*, 37: 234-242.
13. Knight, B.A., B.M. Shields, A. Brook, A. Hill, D.S. Bhat, A.T. Hattersley and C.S. Yajnik, 2015. Lower circulating B₁₂ is associated with higher obesity and insulin resistance during pregnancy in a non-diabetic white British population. *PLOS ONE*, Vol. 10. 10.1371/journal.pone.0135268.
14. Adakalakeswari, A., R. Jayashri, N. Sukumar, H. Venkataraman and R. Pradeepa *et al.*, 2014. Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency is associated with adverse lipid profile in Europeans and Indians with type 2 diabetes. *Cardiovasc. Diabetology*, Vol. 13. 10.1186/s12933-014-0129-4.
15. Aparicio-Ugarriza, R., G. Palacios, M. Alder and M. González-Gross, 2015. A review of the cut-off points for the diagnosis of vitamin B₁₂ deficiency in the general population. *Clin. Chem. Lab. Med. (CCLM)*, 53: 1149-1159.
16. Pfeiffer, C.M., M.R. Sternberg, R.L. Schleicher and M.E. Rybak, 2013. Dietary supplement use and smoking are important correlates of biomarkers of water-soluble vitamin status after adjusting for sociodemographic and lifestyle variables in a representative sample of U.S. adults. *The J. Nutr.*, 143: 957-965.
17. Battat, R., U. Kopylov, A. Szilagy, A. Saxena and D.S. Rosenblatt *et al.*, 2014. Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency in inflammatory bowel disease. *Inflammatory Bowel Dis.*, 20: 1120-1128.
18. Via, M.A. and J.I. Mechanick, 2017. Nutritional and micronutrient care of bariatric surgery patients: Current evidence update. *Curr. Obesity Rep.*, 6: 286-296.
19. Quay, T.A.W., T.H. Schroder, M. Jeruszka-Bielak, W. Li, A.M. Devlin, S.I. Barr and Y. Lamers, 2015. High prevalence of suboptimal vitamin B₁₂ status in young adult women of South Asian and European ethnicity. *Applied Physiol., Nutr., Metab.*, 40: 1279-1286.
20. Allen, L.H., J.W. Miller, L. de Groot, I.H. Rosenberg, A.D. Smith, H. Refsum and D.J. Raiten, 2018. Biomarkers of nutrition for development (BOND): Vitamin B-12 review. *The J. Nutr.*, 148: 1995-2027.
21. Ulvik, A., S.E. Vollset, G. Hoff and P.M. Ueland, 2008. Coffee consumption and circulating B-vitamins in healthy middle-aged men and women. *Clin. Chem.*, 54: 1489-1496.
22. Aroda, V.R., S.L. Edelstein, R.B. Goldberg, W.C. Knowler and S.M. Marcovina *et al.*, 2016. Long-term metformin use and vitamin B₁₂ deficiency in the diabetes prevention program outcomes study. *J. Clin. Endocrinol. Metab.*, 101: 1754-1761.
23. Wilhelm, S.M., R.G. Rjater and P.B. Kale-Pradhan, 2013. Perils and pitfalls of long-term effects of proton pump inhibitors. *Expert Rev. Clin. Pharmacol.*, 6: 443-451.
24. Wong, C.W., 2015. Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency in the elderly: is it worth screening? *Hong Kong Med. J.*, 21: 155-164
25. Palacios, G., R. Sola, L. Barrios, K. Pietrzik, M.J. Castillo and M. González-Gross, 2013. Algorithm for the early diagnosis of vitamin B₁₂ deficiency in elderly people. *Nutr. Hosp.*, 28: 1447-1457.
26. Bailey, R.L., R. Carmel, R. Green, C.M. Pfeiffer and M.E. Cogswell *et al.*, 2011. Monitoring of vitamin B-12 nutritional status in the united states by using plasma methylmalonic acid and serum vitamin B-12. *The Am. J. Clin. Nutr.*, 94: 552-561.
27. El-Khateeb, M., Y. Khader, A. Batieha, H. Jaddou, D. Hyassat, A. Belbisi and K. Ajlouni, 2014. Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency in Jordan: A population-based study. *Ann. Nutr. Metab.*, 64: 101-105.
28. Devi, A., E. Rush, M. Harper and B. Venn, 2018. Vitamin B₁₂ status of various ethnic groups living in New Zealand: An analysis of the adult nutrition survey 2008/2009. *Nutrients*, Vol. 10. 10.3390/nu10020181.
29. Khanduri, U. and A. Sharma, 2007. Megaloblastic anaemia: Prevalence and causative factors. *Natl. Med. J. India* 20: 172-175
30. Ahmed, T., A.S. Rahman, S. Ahmed, A. Siddiqui, A. Javed, J. Kamal and L. Ahmed, 2012. Frequency of vitamin B₁₂ and red cell folate deficiency in macrocytic anaemia. *J. Basic Applied Sci.*, 8: 706-713.
31. Sarode, R., G. Garewal, N. Marwaha, R.K. Marwaha and S. Varma *et al.*, 1989. Pancytopenia in nutritional megaloblastic anaemia. A study from North-West India. *Trop. Geogr. Med.*, 41: 331-346.
32. Sen, K., P. Sinhamahapatra, J. Lalhmachhuana and S. Ray, 2015. A study of clinical profile of vitamin B₁₂ Deficiency with special reference to dermatologic manifestations in a tertiary care hospital in Sub-Himalayan Bengal. *Indian J. Dermatol.*, Vol. 60. 10.4103/0019-5154.160506.
33. Hashim, H. and F. Tahir, 2006. Frequency of vitamin B₁₂ and folic acid deficiencies among patients of megaloblastic anemia. *Ann. Pak. Med. Sci.*, 2: 192-194.
34. Wheeler, L.A., G. Brecher and L.B. Sheiner, 1977. Clinical laboratory use in the evaluation of anemia. *JAMA: The J. Am. Med. Assoc.*, 238: 2709-2714.